

Supplementary Material for: Geographic and temporal morphological stasis in the latest Cretaceous ammonoid *Discoscaphites iris* from the U.S. Gulf and Atlantic Coastal Plains

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Supplementary Figures 1-10.

Full taxonomic description of *Discoscaphites iris*.

Assumed evolutionary relationships.

Supplementary Figure 1: Examples of *Discoscaphites iris* (Conrad, 1858), macroconchs, from sites across the Atlantic and Gulf Coastal Plains. A–B. AMNH 83495 (AMNH loc. 3460). A. right lateral; B. ventral. C–D. AMNH 116150 (AMNH loc. 3458). C. right lateral; D. ventral. E–F. AMNH 115953 (AMNH loc. 3460). E. right lateral; F. ventral. G–H. AMNH 115978

(AMNH loc. 3458). G. right lateral; H. ventral. I–J. AMNH 64572 (AMNH loc. 3481). I. right lateral; J. ventral. K–L. AMNH 115966 (AMNH loc. 3460). K. right lateral; L. ventral. M–N. AMNH 115954 (AMNH loc. 3460). M. left lateral; N. ventral. O–P. 115971 (AMNH loc. 3458). O. right lateral; P. ventral. Q–R. AMNH 115983 (AMNH loc. 3460). Q. right lateral; R. ventral. S–T. AMNH 116148 (AMNH loc. 3458). S. right lateral; T. ventral. U–V. AMNH 116151 (AMNH loc. 3458). U. right lateral; V. ventral. All figures x1.

Supplementary Figure 2: *Discoscaphites iris* (Conrad, 1858), microconchs (A-Z) and macroconchs (a-c) from sites across the Atlantic and Gulf Coastal Plains. A–B. AMNH 77434

(AMNH loc. 3460). A. right lateral; B. ventral. C–D. AMNH 115976 (AMNH loc. 3458). C. left lateral; D. ventral. E–F. AMNH 115974 (AMNH loc. 3458). E. left lateral; F. ventral. G–H. AMNH 115977 (AMNH loc. 3458). G. right lateral; H. ventral. I–J. AMNH 115988 (AMNH loc. 3460). I. left lateral; J. ventral. K–L. AMNH 115990 (AMNH loc. 3460). K. right lateral; L. ventral. M–N. AMNH 112123 (AMNH loc. 3460). M. right lateral; N. ventral. O–P. AMNH 116154 (AMNH loc. 3458). O. left lateral; P. ventral. Q–R. AMNH 115972 (AMNH loc. 3458). Q. left lateral; R. ventral. S–T. AMNH 64556 (AMNH loc. 3481). S. right lateral; T. ventral. U–V. AMNH 64555 (AMNH loc. 3481). U. right lateral; V. ventral. W–X. AMNH 64571 (AMNH loc. 3481). W. right lateral; X. ventral. Y–Z. AMNH 64553 (AMNH loc. 3481). Y. right lateral; Z. ventral. a. AMNH 108178a (AMNH loc. 3620). Left lateral. b. AMNH 111961 (AMNH loc. 3620). Left lateral. c. AMNH 111963 (AMNH loc. 3620). Left lateral.

All figures x1.

Supplementary Figure 3: Relationship between the coefficient of variation (CV) calculated for each morphological trait versus number of specimens measured at each locality. Linear trend lines with r^2 values show generally weak linear relationships. Data are presented separately for macroconchs (black circles and black trendline) and microconchs (white circles and light gray trend line).

Supplementary Figure 4: Relationship between the coefficient of variation (CV) calculated for each morphological trait versus stratigraphic thickness of the *Discoscaphites iris* Zone at each locality. Linear trend lines with r^2 values show generally weak linear relationships. Note that the Owl Creek Type Locality (AMNH loc. 3460) is considerably thicker than other GCP and ACP localities. Data are presented separately for macroconchs (black circles and black trendline) and microconchs (white circles and light gray trend line).

Supplementary Figure 5: Results of Model A (Macroconchs; all localities) size (LMAX) and shape (LMAX/H_p, LMAX/H_s) traits compared against environmental variables: Paleolatitude (Paleolat), Longitude, and grain size (defined as % sand-sized material). Graphs plotted using the visreg package in R.

Supplementary Figure 6: Results of Model A (Macroconch; all localities) shell compression (W_p/H_p , W_s/H_s , W_n/H_h) traits compared against environmental variables: Paleolatitude (Paleolat), Longitude, and grain size (defined as % sand-sized material). Graphs plotted using the visreg package in R.

Supplementary Figure 7: Results of Model B (microconchs; all localities) size (LMAX) and shape (LMAX/H_P) traits compared against environmental variables: Paleolatitude (Paleolat), Longitude, and grain size (defined as % sand-sized material). Graphs plotted using the visreg package in R.

Supplementary Figure 8: Results of Model B (microconchs; all localities) shell compression (W_p/H_p , W_s/H_s , W_h/H_h) traits compared against environmental variables: Paleolatitude (Paleolat), Longitude, and grain size (defined as % sand-sized material). Graphs plotted using the visreg package in R.

Supplementary Figure 9: Results of Model C (macroconchs; localities other than Brazos) size (LMAX) and shape (LMAX/HP, LMAX/Hs) traits compared against environmental variables: Paleolatitude (Paleolat), Longitude, and grain size (defined as % sand-sized material). Graphs plotted using the visreg package in R.

Supplementary Figure 10: Results of Model D (microconchs; localities other than Brazos) size (LMAX) and shape (LMAX/HP, LMAX/Hs) traits compared against environmental variables: Paleolatitude (Paleolat), Longitude, and grain size (defined as % sand-sized material). Graphs plotted using the visreg package in R.

Full taxonomic description of *Discoscaphites iris*

A full description of this species is provided by Landman et al. (2004a, 2004b, 2007). See Landman *et al.* (2010) for an overview of morphological terms associated with scaphitid ammonites. *Discoscaphites iris* (Conrad, 1858) is characterized by easily differentiated dimorphs, separated by morphology and size.

The **adult macroconch** is tightly coiled with a tiny umbilicus. The body chamber occupies approximately on-half whorl and can show a bulge on the umbilical shoulder. There is no gap between the body chamber and the phragmocone. The aperture is constricted and the apertural angle ranges from $\sim 20 - 40^\circ$. The venter and dorsum are slightly projected. The phragmocone is slender and the whorl section is compressed ovoid with maximum width at one-quarter whorl height. The umbilical wall is steep and inclined slightly outward and the umbilical shoulder is gently rounded. In intercostal section, the flanks are flat to broadly rounded and gradually converge toward the venter, becoming more steeply convergent at the site of the inner ventrolateral tubercles. The ventrolateral shoulder is sharply rounded and the venter is nearly flat. The body chamber is fairly robust with a compressed ovoid whorl section. The umbilical wall is steep and convex and the umbilical shoulder is broadly rounded. The inner flanks are nearly flat and inclined outward, the mid flanks are nearly flat to broadly rounded, and the outer flanks between the inner and outer ventrolateral tubercles are flat and converge toward the venter. The ventrolateral shoulder is sharply rounded and the venter is nearly flat.

Ribs on the phragmocone are rectiradiate to prorsiradiate. In coarsely ornamented specimens the ribs are straight and barlike at the adapical end of the exposed phragmocone, but in more finely ornamented specimens the ribs are slightly flexuous, curving backward on the inner flanks, forward and then backward on the midflanks, and forward again on the outer

flanks, crossing the venter with a slight adoral projection. Intercalation and branching occur at one-third and two-thirds whorl height. The ribs become broader, straighter, and more widely spaced toward the adoral end of the phragmocone. They tend to weaken on the venter, forming indistinct swellings, before disappearing altogether. In coarsely ornamented specimens, four rows of tubercles (umbilicolateral, flank, and inner and outer ventrolateral tubercles) are already present on the adapical end of the exposed phragmocone. In more finely ornamented specimens, one or two rows of ventrolateral tubercles are visible on the phragmocone, mostly commonly the outer row. Two additional rows appear on the flanks across the transition into the body chamber. The tubercles occur on broad, low convex ribs that become more prominent on the hook. All the tubercles end in sharp points. The most prominent tubercles are the two umbilicolateral tubercles on the midshaft just below the umbilical margin. Flank tubercles are slightly smaller than the umbilicolateral tubercles and occur midway between the umbilicolateral and inner ventrolateral tubercles.

The **adult microconch** is generally smaller than the macroconch, although the two dimorphs do overlap for part of their size range. The shell is tightly coiled, but unlike macroconchs, the umbilical seam of microconchs follows the curvature of the venter. There is a very small gap between the phragmocone and body chamber. The end of the phragmocone occurs at the line of maximum length, and the body chamber occupies approximately one-half whorl. The aperture is constricted and the venter and dorsum are slightly projected. The whorl section of the phragmocone is a compressed ovoid. The umbilical wall is steep and subvertical and the umbilical shoulder is sharply rounded. The inner flanks are flat and slightly divergent, the midflanks are flat to broadly rounded, and the outer flanks between the inner and outer ventrolateral tubercles are flat and gently converge to the venter. The ventrolateral shoulder is relatively sharply rounded and the venter is nearly flat. In passing into the body chamber, whorl width expands more rapidly than whorl height, producing a swollen whorl section at midshaft.

The umbilical whorl is broad, steep, and subvertical and the umbilical shoulder is abruptly rounded. The inner flanks are flat and slightly divergent, the midflanks are flat to broadly rounded, and the outer flanks are flat to convergent. The ventrolateral shoulder is broadly to sharply rounded and the venter is nearly flat.

The phragmocone is covered with prorsiradiate straight ribs. In coarsely ornamented forms, the ribs are barlike, whereas in more finely ornamented forms, the ribs are slightly flexuous. Branching and intercalations occur at one-third and two-thirds whorl height. The ventral ribs are faint, straight, and swollen and join ventrolateral tubercles on either side of the venter. Both rows of ventrolateral tubercles are present at the adapical end of the exposed phragmocone and the other two rows appear soon thereafter. Tubercles in all four rows gradually become more widely spaced toward the adoral end of the phragmocone. The ornament on the body chamber consists of swollen, poorly defined prorsiradiate ribs bearing four rows of tubercles, of which the umbilicolateral tubercles are the most prominent. Ribs are only conspicuous near the aperture. Tubercles are perched on the umbilical shoulder and attain their greatest height just adoral of midshaft. Both outer and inner ventrolateral tubercles are smaller and more closely spaced on the hook. Outer ventrolateral tubercles are matched or offset on either side of the venter. The suture of *D. iris* is the same for both dimorphs; with a broad first lateral saddle and an asymmetrically bifid first lateral lobe.

Assumed evolutionary relationships

Discoscaphites iris forms a clade with the co-occurring species *Discoscaphites sphaeroidalis* Kennedy and Cobban, 2000, *Discoscaphites minardi* Landman et al. 2004a, *Discoscaphites jerseyensis* Landman et al. 2007, and probably the recently described *Discoscaphites mullinaxorum* Witts et al. 2021. All are found in the upper Maastrichtian of the Gulf (except *D. jerseyensis*) and Atlantic (except *D. mullinaxorum*) Coastal Plains of the USA.

Its evolutionary lineage probably lies with *D. minardi* and the older *Discoscaphites conradi* (Morton, 1834), as well as *D. gulosus* (Morton, 1834) and *D. rossi* Landman and Waage, 1993 found in the mid-upper Maastrichtian of the Gulf and Atlantic Coastal Plains and the US Western Interior (Landman and Waage 1993). These hypothesized relationships are supported by preliminary phylogenetic analyses of *Discoscaphites* in North America (Main text Fig. 2) (Landman et al. 2007).

Discoscaphites iris differs from *Discoscaphites sphaeroidalis* in having a less inflated phragmocone with a wider venter and a less robust body chamber. In addition, the flanks of the phragmocone in *D. sphaeroidalis* are covered with narrow, long ribs. *D. iris* differs from *Discoscaphites minardi* in having a more robust body chamber with inflated rather than flat flanks, more sharply pointed, conical flank tubercles, which are absent or weak in *D. minardi*, and coarser ribbing at the aperture. *Discoscaphites jerseyensis* resembles *D. minardi*, but with a more robust body chamber, very fine ribbing on the hook, and a row of midflank bullae instead of tubercles, which also distinguishes it from *D. iris*. *Discoscaphites mullinaxorum* is a lot smaller than *D. iris*, with flatter flanks and more delicate ornament. Species-specific characters are thus generally distinct from the measured traits analysed in this study.

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